

Synthesis, spectral, cyclic voltammetric and biological studies of some oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of a Schiff base derived from 4-aminoantipyrine

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Abstract : A few mononuclear complexes of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) with a Schiff base derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and *o*-vanillin have been synthesized and characterized by elemental, spectral (IR, electronic, ESR and NMR) analysis, conductance measurements and cyclic voltammetric studies. The complexes have general formulae $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_2\text{X}]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPOV})\text{ClX}]$ where AAPOV = 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzylidene amino)pyrazol-5-one and X = Cl, NCS, NO_3 or ClO_4 . The ESR spectrum of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$ in the solid state exhibits a single line pattern. The ESR parameters were calculated and the g_{av} value (1.9795) shows that the complex is monomeric with Mo in the +5 oxidation state. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$ have been examined and found to be orthorhombic with unit cell dimensions $a = 16.8088 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.7467 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 7.4816 \text{ \AA}$. The thermal decomposition behaviour of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$ was studied using TG and DTG techniques. The complex is stable up to 270 °C and then undergoes decomposition in three stages. The kinetic parameters were calculated using the Coats-Redfern equation. The cyclic voltammetric profile of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ shows a quasi-reversible peak attributable to $\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}$ redox system. The energy minimized computer model of the ligand and one of its complexes were also constructed.

Keywords : Orthovanillin, Schiff base, thermal studies.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) has gained immense importance because molybdenum is one of the most biologically active transition metals. Studies on several molybdenum complexes aim at devising model system for imitating the enzyme activities and many other processes of biological interest. Complexes of MoO^{V} and MoO_2^{VI} with ligands derived from biologically active compound 4-aminoantipyrine have been reported^{1,2}. We report here the synthesis and characterization of some new complexes of these oxo cations with the potential tridentate ligand 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzylidene amino)pyrazol-5-one (AAPOV) (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

All the complexes are brown coloured non hygroscopic solids. The analytical data of all the complexes presented

Fig. 1

in Table 1 corresponds to MoOLCl_2X and MoO_2LCIX for Mo^{V} and Mo^{VI} complexes respectively where L = AAPOV and X = Cl, NCS, NO_3 / ClO_4 .

IR spectra :

The important IR spectral bands of the ligand and the complexes along with their probable assignments are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Analytical data of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of AAPOV

Complex (Colour)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Molar conductance $\times 10^{-3} M (\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1})$			μ_{eff}
	Mo	C	H	N	Cl	S	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2$	CH_3CN	CH_3OH	
[MoO(AAPOV)Cl ₃] Brown	16.59 (16.68)	37.51 (37.58)	2.91 (2.95)	9.71 (9.74)	18.09 (18.5)	-	1.8	18.6	16.6	1.78
[MoO(AAPOV)(NCS)Cl ₂] Brown	15.91 (16.05)	38.09 (38.17)	2.82 (2.84)	11.68 (11.71)	11.82 (11.87)	5.31 (5.35)	3.4	10.1	14.1	1.68
[MoO(AAPOV)(NO ₃)Cl ₂] Light brown	15.82 (15.94)	35.89 (35.92)	2.79 (2.82)	11.62 (11.64)	11.75 (11.79)	-	2.6	9.8	12.8	1.85
[MoO(AAPOV)(ClO ₄)Cl ₂] Dark brown	15.0 (15.01)	33.78 (33.81)	2.62 (2.66)	8.72 (8.76)	-	-	3.4	12.6	18.1	1.83
[MoO ₂ (AAPOV)Cl ₂] Light brown	17.11 (17.26)	38.81 (38.89)	3.01 (3.06)	10.02 (10.08)	12.73 (12.76)	-	2.6	8.9	11.8	Diamagnetic
[MoO ₂ (AAPOV)(NCS)Cl] Dark brown	16.48 (16.59)	39.38 (39.45)	2.91 (2.94)	12.08 (12.11)	6.09 (6.13)	5.49 (5.53)	1.9	12.1	9.5	-
[MoO ₂ (AAPOV)(NO ₃)Cl] Dark brown	16.41 (16.48)	37.01 (37.12)	2.89 (2.92)	12.00 (12.03)	6.01 (6.09)	-	2.4	11.8	8.9	-
[MoO ₂ (AAPOV)(ClO ₄)Cl] Brown	15.42 (15.48)	34.81 (34.87)	2.71 (2.74)	9.02 (9.04)	-	-	3.4	12.1	12.8	-

The IR spectrum of the ligand exhibits a broad band at 2980 cm^{-1} , assignable to hydrogen bonded -OH group¹⁻³. In the spectra of the complexes, a new broad band of medium intensity appears $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, suggestive of free -OH group and hence its nonparticipation in coordination⁴. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of pyrazolone moiety appeared at 1660 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is shifted to 1600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes, indicating participation of the carbonyl group in coordination^{5,6}. The band due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ observed as a strong band at 1590 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is shifted to a lower frequency by 20–30 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the complexes, suggestive of participation of the azomethine nitrogen in coordination⁷. Thus AAPOV acts as a neutral bidentate ligand in these complexes, coordinating through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen.

IR spectra of Mo^V complexes show a strong band occurring $\sim 950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of Mo=O stretching frequency⁸. The presence of two strong bands in the regions 905–910 cm^{-1} and 945–950 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ respectively in the spectra of the Mo^{VI} complexes is indicative of *cis*-MoO₂²⁺ structure^{9,10}. The weak bands at 500–520 cm^{-1} and at 430–440 cm^{-1} are assignable to $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ respectively¹¹. In the IR spectra of the thiocyanato com-

plexes of Mo^V and Mo^{VI}, very strong band at 2050 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{C-N}}$) along with medium intensity bands at 830 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{C-S}}$) and 490 cm^{-1} (δ_{NCS}) are suggestive of N-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate in group¹². The nitrate complexes of both oxocations exhibit two strong bands at 1490 cm^{-1} (ν_5) and 1390 cm^{-1} (ν_1) with a difference of 110 cm^{-1} indicating unidentate coordination¹³.

In the spectra of the perchlorate complexes, strong bands $\sim 1150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1070 cm^{-1} (split components of ν_3) and medium band ~ 630 and 610 cm^{-1} (split components of ν_4) along with medium intensity bands at 920 cm^{-1} (ν_2) shows the presence of unidentately coordinated perchlorate group¹⁴.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand shows three sharp singlets at δ 2.41, 3.41 and 3.93 ppm corresponding to protons on C-CH₃, N-CH₃ and O-CH₃ respectively. The multiplet between δ 7.27–7.51 is assignable to phenyl ring protons of the antipyrine moiety¹⁵. The phenyl protons of the vanillin moiety appear as a multiplet between δ 6.81–7.00. A detailed assignment of the aromatic protons is not attempted. The signal due to phenolic -OH proton¹⁶ is observed as a singlet at δ 13.86. The singlet at δ 9.81 is assignable to azomethine proton. All the signals in the NMR spectrum of AAPOV are retained in the

Table 2. Infrared spectral data of AAPOV (L) and its MoO^V and MoO₂^{VI} complexes

AAPOV	[MoOLCl ₃] [MoOL(NCS)Cl ₂] [MoOL(NO ₃)Cl ₂] [MoOL(ClO ₄)Cl ₂] [MoO ₂ LCl ₂] [MoO ₂ L(NCS)Cl] [MoO ₂ L(NO ₃)Cl] [MoO ₂ L(ClO ₄)Cl]	Assignments	
2980 <i>bm</i>	3420 <i>bm</i>	3420 <i>bm</i>	VO-H free
	3400 <i>bm</i>	3410 <i>bm</i>	VO-H hydrogen bonded
	2050 <i>vs</i>	2050 <i>vs</i>	VC=N of thiocyanate
1660 <i>s</i>	1605 <i>s</i>	1600 <i>s</i>	VC=O pyrazolone
1590 <i>s</i>	1565 <i>s</i>	1565 <i>s</i>	VC-N of azomethine
	1490 <i>s</i>	1490 <i>s</i>	V ₅ (NO ₃) coordinated
	1380 <i>s</i>	1380 <i>s</i>	V ₁ (NO ₃) coordinated
		1150 <i>s</i>	V ₃ (ClO ₄) coordinated
		1070 <i>s</i>	V ₃ (ClO ₄) coordinated
	1020 <i>m</i>	1020 <i>m</i>	V ₂ (NO ₃) coordinated
	967 <i>vs</i>	960 <i>vs</i>	V _{Mo=O}
	960 <i>vs</i>	945 <i>vs</i>	V _{sym} (O=Mo=O)
		920 <i>m</i>	V ₂ (ClO ₄) coordinated
		910 <i>vs</i>	V _{asym} (O=Mo=O)
	830 <i>m</i>	830 <i>m</i>	VC-S of thiocyanate
		630 <i>m</i>	V ₄ (ClO ₄) coordinated
		620 <i>m</i>	V ₄ (ClO ₄) coordinated
	520 <i>w</i>	510 <i>w</i>	V _{Mo=O}
	510 <i>w</i>	510 <i>w</i>	δ _{NCS} of thiocyanate
	490 <i>s</i>	490 <i>s</i>	
435 <i>w</i>	435 <i>w</i>	435 <i>w</i>	V _{Mo-N}

spectra of the complexes. The presence of OH proton signal at δ 13.82 in the spectra of the complexes support the IR spectral evidence of non participation of -OH group in coordination.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral data of the ligand and Mo^V complexes with their tentative assignments are given in Table 3. The electronic spectrum of the ligand shows an intense band at 270 nm. A similar band occurs at 330

Table 3. The electronic spectral data of MoO^V complexes
 λ_{\max} nm

Ligand	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	Change transfer	$b_2 \rightarrow b_1$	$b_2 \rightarrow e$
AAPOV (L)	270	330	-	-	-
[MoO(L)Cl ₃]	270	330	420	505	670
[MoO(L)(NCS)Cl ₂]	275	340	415	505	650
[MoO(L)(NO ₃)Cl ₂]	270	336	417	505	675
[MoO(L)(ClO ₄)Cl ₂]	270	330	420	510	650

nm. These are assigned to the electronic transitions $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ respectively¹⁷. All the four Mo^V complexes have similar absorption peaks in their spectra. The band ~ 420 nm may be attributed to charge transfer transition $O(\pi) \rightarrow d(\text{Mo})$. The medium band at 505 nm and weak broad band in the region 650-670 nm are assignable to d-d transitions¹⁸.

ESR spectra :

The X-band ESR spectrum of the complex [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃] recorded at room temperature in the solid state (poly crystalline) (Fig. 2) exhibits a single line pattern. The ESR parameters calculated from the spectrum are $g_{\parallel} = 2.0112$, $g_{\perp} = 1.9479$ and $g_{\text{av}} = 1.9795$. The calculated g_{av} value shows that complex is monomeric with Mo in the +5 oxidation state¹⁹.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The electrochemical behaviour of the complex [MoO(AAPOV)(NO₃)Cl₂] was studied in deaerated acetonitrile at a concentration of 10^{-3} M. The working electrode used was glassy carbon with Pt auxiliary electrode and SCE as the reference electrode. The cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 3) was recorded between switching potentials -2000 mV and +2000 mV at a scan rate of 100 mV/s. Tetrabutyl ammonium hexa fluoro phosphate was used as the supporting electrolyte and ferrocene was used as internal standard. The complex shows a quasi-reversible peak around -1000 mV. This can be attributed to the Mo^V/Mo^{IV} redox system.

Thermal studies :

The thermal decomposition behaviour of the complex [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃] was studied in static air at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The TG and DTG curves are given in Fig. 4. The complex is stable up to 270 °C as indicated by the plateau up to this temperature. It then undergoes decomposition in three stages. The decomposition is complete at 780 °C as evident from the TG curve and the final product is found to be MoO₃. The mass loss data obtained from the TG experiment (74.01%) and the independent pyrolysis experiment (75.27%) are in good agreement with the theoretical value (74.08%) for MoO₃ as the final residue. The computational details of the first stages of decomposition of the complex is given in Table 4. The kinetic parameters for the three stages (Table 5) of decomposition of the complex was evaluated using Coats-Redfern equation. The order parameters for the three stages of decomposition (stage-1, Fig. 5) of decomposition are 2.5, 0.8 and 2. The Coats-Redfern plot of stage one decomposition of the complex is given in Fig. 5. The values of correlation coefficient are very close to

Fig. 2. ESR spectrum of [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃].

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of [MoO(AAPOV)(NO₃)Cl₂].

unity indicating that the kinetic parameters calculated fit perfectly with the experiment.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complex [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃] recorded (Fig. 6) by powder method were successfully indexed for orthorhombic system using Lipson's method²⁰ (Table 6).

The lattice constants for the complex are $A = 0.0021$, $B = 0.0043$ and $C = 0.0106$ and hence the unit cell dimensions calculated are $a = 16.8088 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.7467 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 7.4816 \text{ \AA}$.

Fig. 4. TG/DTG curves of [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃].

Table 4. Computational details of first stage of thermal decomposition of [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃]

<i>m</i>	<i>T</i> (K)	RT	<i>w</i>	α	$g\alpha$	CR
3.37	553	1.8083	0	0	0	-
3.34	563	1.7762	0.03	0.02913	0.0302	-16.1656
3.27	573	1.7452	0.1	0.0970	0.1103	-14.9057
3.14	583	1.7152	0.23	0.2233	0.3072	-13.9164
2.96	593	1.6863	0.41	0.3980	0.7608	-13.0437
2.79	603	1.6583	0.58	0.5631	1.6419	-12.3079
2.66	613	1.6313	0.71	0.6893	3.1831	-11.6788
2.56	623	1.6051	0.81	0.7864	6.0868	-11.0629
2.48	633	1.57978	0.89	0.8640	12.6370	-10.3643
2.40	643	1.5521	0.97	0.9417	46.7507	-9.0874
2.34	653	1.5319	1.03	1	-	-

$$CR = \ln \frac{g\alpha}{T^2}, RT = \frac{1 \times 10^3}{T}$$

Table 5. Kinetic parameters for the three stages of thermal decomposition of [MoO(AAPOV)Cl₃]

Stage	Peak temp. (°C)	Activation energy (<i>E</i>) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Pre-exponential term (<i>A</i>) (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation (ΔS) (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
I	570	246.28	3.82×10^{36}	449.31
II	747	285.11	1.97×10^{33}	380.76
III	1036	741.17	4.66×10^{73}	1155.23

Antimicrobial studies :

The ligand and the complex [MoO(AAPOV)(NCS)Cl₂] were screened for their antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* by Agar diffusion method²¹. The test results (Table 7) show that both the ligand and the complex have no antibacterial activity against both gram positive *S. aureus* and gram negative

Fig. 5. Coats-Redfern plot of stage I decomposition of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$.

Experimental

MoCl_5 (Acros Organics, USA), MoO_3 (LoboChemie, Mumbai) and 4-aminoantipyrine (Fluka, Switzerland), *o*-vanillin (Acros Organics, USA) were used as such. All other chemicals were of BDH A.R. grade.

Metal, chloride, sulphur and perchlorate in the complexes were estimated by standard methods²². Microanalysis (CHN) was done at RSIC, Lucknow. The IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO/FTIR 430 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. The electronic spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in methanol. ESR spectrum was recorded in the solid state (polycrystalline form) at room temperature with DPPH as reference material. The molar conductance of the complexes in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$,

Fig. 6. X-Ray powder diffraction patterns of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$.

E. coli at the concentrations tested under the test conditions.

Based on the analytical, spectral (IR, UV-Vis, NMR and ESR) and electrochemical data, distorted octahedral structures (Figs. 7 and 8) have been tentatively proposed for all the MoO^{V} and MoO_2^{VI} complexes.

Computer modeling :

The computer models of the proposed configuration of the ligand AAPOV and the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$ were constructed by using the software Hyperchem 7.5. The geometrical optimization of the structure obtained are presented in Figs. 9 and 10.

$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and CH_3CN ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) were measured at $300 \pm 2 \text{ K}$ using an Elico conductivity bridge type CM 82 T with a dip type cell fitted with platinum electrodes (cell constant 0.995 cm^{-1}). The magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature ($300 \pm 2 \text{ K}$) were measured on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections for various atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal's constants and TIP for $\text{Mo}^{5+} = 55 \times 10^{-6} \text{ CGS units}$ were also incorporated²³. Cyclic voltammetric profile of one of the complexes was run on a BAS-CV-50W voltammetric analyzer using glassy carbon as the working electrode. The X-ray powder diffrac-

Table 6. X-Ray diffraction data of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$

Line	<i>hkl</i>	$\text{Sin}^2\theta$ (obs.)	$\text{Sin}^2\theta$ (cal.)	Relative intensity (%)
1	200	0.0086	0.0084	23.10
2	001	0.0116	0.0106	100.00
3	101	0.0126	0.0127	30.71
4	011	0.0147	0.0149	73.25
5	120	0.0194	0.0193	41.16
6	310	0.0227	0.0232	8.23
7	220	0.0253	0.0256	26.35
8	021	0.0273	0.0278	43.77
9	121	0.0291	0.0299	12.07
10	311	0.0334	0.0338	16.63
11	320	0.0355	0.0361	62.29
12	002	0.0419	0.0424	17.20
13	102	0.0434	0.0445	18.75
14	021	0.0499	0.0493	5.37
15	121	0.0519	0.0514	60.73
16	022	0.0591	0.0596	16.88
17	302	0.0611	0.0613	6.88
18	312	0.0661	0.0656	20.10
19	430	0.0716	0.0723	4.06
20	322	0.0774	0.0785	10.53
21	032	0.0808	0.0811	3.69
22	132	0.0834	0.0832	1.81
23	232	0.0873	0.0895	1.05
24	530	0.0910	0.0912	2.97
25	502	0.0943	0.0949	6.22
26	341	0.0988	0.0983	8.77
27	213	0.1074	0.1081	6.02

Table 7. The result of antimicrobial activity of AAPOV and $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}_2]$

Sample	Concentration per disc	Zone of inhibition	
		<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 25923
AAPOV	10 μg	0	0
	20 μg	0	0
	40 μg	0	0
	80 μg	0	0
	160 μg	0	0
$[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}_2]$	10 μg	0	0
	20 μg	0	0
	40 μg	0	0
	80 μg	0	0
	160 μg	0	0
Gentamycin	10 mcg	22 mm	23 mm
Negative control		0	0

X = Cl, NO₃, NCS or ClO₄
Fig. 7. Suggested structure for $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_2\text{X}]$.

X = Cl, NO₃, NCS or ClO₄
Fig. 8. Suggested structure for $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPOV})\text{ClX}]$.

Figs. 9 and 10. Energy minimized configuration of AAPOV and $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPOV})\text{Cl}_3]$.

tion patterns of one of the complexes were recorded using Philips X-ray PW 1710 diffractometer. Molecular mechanics calculations were done with Hyperchem Release 7.5 professional version, an interactive graphics program that allows rapid structure building, geometry optimization and molecular display²⁴. Molecular modeling software Hyperchem has the ability to handle transition metal complexes. Energy minimization was repeated several times to find global minimum.

Synthesis of the ligand :

The ligand was prepared by mixing methanolic solutions of 4-aminoantipyrine (5 g, 25 mmol) and *o*-vanillin (3.8 g, 25 mmol) in the cold. The yellow crystalline product separated instantaneously was suction filtered, washed with small amounts of methanol and recrystallised from hot methanol.

Synthesis of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes :

A methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (2 mmol) was added to a hot solution of the ligand (2 mmol) slowly with good stirring. The brown coloured solution formed was refluxed for ~1 h on a water bath. The precipitated complex was suction filtered, washed, several times with aqueous methanol (1 : 1) followed by ether and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

A general method was adopted for the synthesis of the thiocyanato, nitrate and perchlorato complexes. A methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (2 mmol) containing ~0.5 g of NH₄CNS or ~0.5 g of LiNO₃ or 3–4 drops of HClO₄ as the case may be, was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring. The resulting solution was refluxed on a water for ~1 h. The complex formed was suction filtered, washed with aqueous methanol (1 : 1) followed by dry ether and then dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

Synthesis of dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes :

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of these dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes. MoO₃ (2 mmol) was dissolved in minimum quantity of conc. HCl. The solution was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring. The resulting brown solution was refluxed on a water bath for ~2 h. The solid complex separated out was suction filtered washed with aqueous methanol (1 : 1) followed by ether and then dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

A general method was adopted for the preparation of thiocyanato, nitrate and perchlorato complexes. A solution of MoO₃ (2 mmol) dissolved in minimum quantity of conc. HCl containing ~0.5 g of NH₄CNS/ ~0.5 g LiNO₃/ 2–3 drops of HClO₄ as the case may be, was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with stirring. The resulting solution was refluxed on a water bath for ~2 h. The solid complex separated out was washed, with aqueous methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

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